

Clinico Cyto Histopathological Correlation in Breast Carcinoma and Correlation with Various Prognostic Markers

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Abstract:

Background: Carcinoma breast is the most common malignancy occurring in females worldwide while in India it is the 2nd most common malignancy occurring after cervical cancer. The incidence is three times higher in urban areas than in rural setup. The disease pattern, clinical and histopathological presentation differs from that of the western world. It needs alarming attention because it causes high morbidity and mortality.

Methods: This is a Hospital based observational study done for a period of 1 year 10 months at king George hospital, Visakhapatnam. Among the patients with breast lump who attended surgical OPD and gynecology OPD, 182 patients were subjected to FNAC, Histopathology and IHC.

Results: Breast carcinoma is most common in the age group of 41-50yrs with 35.7% followed by 51-60yrs with 28.6%. Among the 113 cases, 110 (97%) were Invasive breast Carcinoma NOS type, 1 (1%) were Mucinous carcinoma, 1 (1%) was Tubular carcinoma, 1(1%) was Metaplastic carcinoma. According to Modified Bloom-Richardson scoring system, among 113 cases 77 cases (68%) were in grade II, 23cases (20%) were in grade III and 13 cases (12%) in grade I. among the 100 cases, estrogen and progesterone receptors were positive in 23 cases, estrogen receptor was positive in 8 cases, progesterone receptor was positive in 3 cases, while both receptors were negative in 66 cases. Estrogen receptor, progesterone receptor or both were positive in (34 cases) 34 % whereas Estrogen receptor, progesterone receptor or both were negative in (66cases) 66%. Out of 100 breast carcinoma patients show 24 cases positive (24%) and 76 cases (76%) were found to be negative.

Summary:

- The peak age of incidence of breast carcinoma in present study is 41 to 50 years.
- IAC grading of cytological smears is found to show high correlation with Histopathological picture. Hence this will assist to bring uniformity of reporting among pathologists and in predicting aggressiveness of tumor.
- Among the various histological variants of breast carcinoma, Invasive breast carcinoma – NOS type constituted 97%.
- Grade II tumors accounted for 68% of tumors in the present study population.
- Estrogen, Progesterone receptor or both are found to be positive in 34% while 66% showed negativity.
- HER-2 /neu over expression is seen in 24% of tumors and not seen in 76% of tumors.
- Out of 65 cases, 15 were T1, 46 were T2 and 4 cases were T3 tumors. smaller the tumor size more is the receptor positivity. This inverse relationship showed statistical significance (p value=0.005).
- HER-2/neu over expression showed a trend of increased positivity up to 5cm.

Conclusion: IAC grading of cytology smears is found to be useful in standardization of reporting. Estrogen, progesterone positivity is more in smaller sized tumors. Her-2/nue over expression is seen among nodal positive cases. Higher tumor grade is associated with advanced clinical stage. Lymphnode metastasis is associated with higher tumor grade. Incidence of triple negative tumors is more among Indian population when compared to western world.

Keywords: Breast Carcinoma, Prognostic Factors In Carcinoma Breast, Cytological Grading In Breast Carcinoma.

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Introduction

Carcinoma breast is the most common malignancy occurring in females worldwide while in India it is the 2nd most common malignancy occurring after cervical cancer [1]. The incidence is three times higher in urban areas than in rural setup [2]. The disease pattern, clinical and histopathological presentation differs from that of the western world. It needs alarming attention because it causes high morbidity and mortality [3]. There is a need to understand the initiation and progression of breast cancer on hormonal, cellular and molecular basis which forms the platform for designing of targeted therapy.

Prognosis and management of breast carcinoma are influenced by the classic variables such as histological type and grade, tumor size, lymph node status, Estrogen, Progesterone receptor status and HER-2/neu over expression. Patients with ER-positive/PR-positive tumors have a better prognosis than patients with ER negative/PR-negative tumors. HER2/neu status became clinically relevant with the demonstration that HER-2/neu positive tumors have a worse prognosis than HER2/neu negative tumors. [2] It has been recognized that HER2/neu over expression served as both a marker of aggressive disease and a target for treatment.

Aims and Objectives:

1. To correlate clinical, cytological and histological findings.
2. To evaluate the distribution of Estrogen, Progesterone receptors and HER-2/neu in breast malignancies by using Immunohistochemical method
3. To find out the correlation of Estrogen, Progesterone receptors and HER-2/neu status with other possible variables.

Materials and Methods:

This is a Hospital based observational study done for a period of 1 year 10 months at king George hospital, Visakhapatnam. Among the patients with breast lump who attended surgical OPD and gynecology OPD, 182 patients were subjected to FNAC, Histopathology and IHC.

Inclusion Criteria: Includes all clinically suspected, FNAC positive breast lesions, trucut, Lumpectomy and radical mastectomy specimens of breast Carcinoma.

Exclusion Criteria: Includes known cases of breast carcinoma with preoperative chemo or Radiotherapy, male breast cancers, those who are not willing to give consent.

Results

A total of 182 cases were taken for study during the period of January 2021 and October 2022. Out of them 113 were modified radical mastectomy specimens, remaining 69 were trucut biopsy specimens.

Out of 113 MRM specimens 65 randomly selected cases were tested for immunohistochemistry, and out of 69 trucut biopsy specimens 35 randomly selected cases were tested for immunohistochemistry.

Breast carcinoma is most common in the age group of 41-50yrs with 35.7% followed by 51-60yrs with 28.6%. Among the 113 cases, 110 (97%) were Invasive breast Carcinoma NOS type, 1 (1%) were Mucinous carcinoma, 1 (1%) was Tubular carcinoma, 1(1%) was Metaplastic carcinoma.

According to Modified Bloom-Richardson scoring system, among 113 cases 77 cases (68%) were in grade II, 23cases (20%) were in grade III and 13 cases (12%) in grade I.

Table 1: Show the distribution of histological grading in breast carcinoma

S. No.	Histological grade	No. of cases	percentage
1	Grade I	13	12%
2	Grade 2	77	68%
3	Grade 3	23	20%
	Total No. of cases	113	

In correlation between Estrogen receptors and Progesterone receptors among the 100 cases, estrogen and progesterone receptors were positive in 23 cases, estrogen receptor was positive in 8 cases, progesterone receptor was positive in 3

cases, while both receptors were negative in 66 cases. Estrogen receptor, progesterone receptor or both were positive in (34 cases) 34 % whereas Estrogen receptor, progesterone receptor or both were negative in (66cases) 66%.

Table 2: Show correlation between Estrogen receptors and Progesterone receptors

S. No	Group	No. of cases	percentages
1	Er +/Pr+	23	23%
2	Er - /Pr+	3	3%
3	Er +/Pr-	8	8%
4	Er - /Pr-	66	66%
	Total cases	100	

HER-2/neu over expression in 100 breast carcinoma patients show 24 cases positive (24%) and 76 cases (76%) were found to be negative.

In correlation of hormone receptors with tumor size a total of 65 MRM cases were taken. Among T1 cases 66% showed receptor positivity, 21 % of T2

sized tumors, and 25% of T3 sized tumors showed positivity. The receptor status was found to be comparatively reduced in larger sized tumors as depicted.

This correlation was statistically analyzed and found to be significant (P value 0.005).

Table 3: Show correlation of hormone receptors with tumor size

S. No	Tumor size	Total	Er/pr positive	percentage
1	T1 \leq 2cm	15	10	66%
2	T2 > 2 – 5 cm	46	10	21%
3	T3 >5cm	4	1	25%
	Total No. of Cases	65		

HER-2/neu overexpression was noted in 2% of T1 sized tumors, 34% of T2 sized tumors and 0% of T3 sized tumors (P value 0.121). In **correlation of hormone receptors with Histological grading** show Estrogen, Progesterone receptor positivity in 28% of grade I tumors, 34% of grade II tumors and 33% of grade III tumors.(P value 0.905).

In **correlation of HER-2/neu with histological grading** it was found that HER-2/neu over expression was seen in 9% of grade I tumors, 36% of grade II tumors and 33% of grade III tumors. (P value 0.076).

In **correlation of hormone receptors with nodal status** out of 65 patients 41 had nodal metastasis, among them 12 (29%) showed receptor positivity. Out of 24 nodal negative patients, the receptor status was positive in 9 (38%) patients. This explains higher receptor expression in nodal negative patients. (P value 0.494).

In **correlation of HER-2/neu with nodal status** Out of 65 patients, HER-2/neu over expression was seen in 41% of nodal positive as opposed to 4% of

nodal negative patients. The correlation was statistically analyzed and found to be significant (P value 0.001). In **correlation of receptor status with oncoprotein expression** among 100 cases 9 cases were both ER\PR and HER-2/neu positive, whereas 51 were both negative. (P value 0.678)

In **correlation of clinical stage with Histopathological grade** the present study showed that higher clinical stage is associated with tumors of higher grade. This correlation was statistically analyzed and found to be significant (P value 0.002).

In **correlation of lymphnode metastasis with Histopathological grade** out of 78 nodal metastases 12 were grade I, 53 were grade II and 13 were grade III. This correlation was statistically analyzed and found to be significant (P value 0.001).

Correlation of cytology with histopathology shows out of 113 Total modified radical mastectomy Cases IAC grade shows more predominance of C5.

Figure 1: showing pleomorphic ductal epithelial cells, few showing prominent nucleoli (H & E) 40X

Figure 2: Invasive Breast Carcinoma- Moderately differentiated (H & E) 10X

Figure 3: Tumor cells showing membrane positivity for her-2/neu- (IHC) 40X

Figure 4: Tumor cells showing strong nuclear staining- progesterone receptor positivity – (IHC) 40X

Discussion

Age of Occurrence: The present study in concurrence with Shreshtha Malvia⁴ et al. showed that the age of peak occurrence of malignancy is 41–50 years group.

Correlation of cytology with histopathology: In the present study out of 113 patients 108 patients were reported as C 5 and 5 were C 4 on the appearance of their cytology samples showing a highly positive correlation, correlated well with studies of Varsha chauhan et al [5] and Hemlata Panwar et al [6].

Distribution of Histological variants of Breast carcinoma; The incidence encountered by Dixon et al [7]., Omar Hameed et al [8]., and Puvitha et al [9]., were comparable with present study. The most common histological type in accordance with the other results was Invasive breast carcinoma – NOS type accounting for 97%.

Hormone Receptor status in breast carcinomas: Desai et al [10] in the year 2000 studied the Estrogen, Progesterone receptors status of breast carcinoma in India. Out of 798 tumors, 260(32.6%) showed estrogen receptor positivity and 368 (46.1%) showed progesterone receptor positivity. Puvitha et al [9] (2010) in her study found that Estrogen, Progesterone receptor or both were positive in 51.6% cases and both receptors were negative in 48.4% cases. HER-2/neu over expression was in 42.7% cases. In the present study we found that estrogen, progesterone or both were positive in 44% of cases. Both the receptors were negative in 66% of cases (table No: 4). This is more in concordance with the study done by Desai et al [10]., where he found that the study population showed more percentage of receptor non-reactive cases.

Correlation of age with receptors status; Puvitha et al [9] in her study noticed that receptor positivity was 77.77% in patients older than 50 years age group, In the present study the hormone receptor expression increased with age up to 60 years. After 60 years tumors showed non-reactive status.

Estrogen, Progesterone receptor, HER-2/neu with other variables S.Goyle et al [11] in 2008 conducted a retrospective study in India. They reviewed 131 patients and found that receptor and oncoprotein expression does not necessarily correlate with advanced tumors in our population. In the present study Estrogen, Progesterone receptor positivity was seen 28% of grade I tumors, 34% of grade II tumors and 33% of grade III tumors (table No:8). Slight increase in receptor expression is seen as the tumor grade increased. This is more in concordance with study of S.Goyle et al [11]., where receptor status and oncoprotein

expression did not show any correlation with tumor grade.

In the present study, among T1 cases 66% showed receptor positivity, 21 % of T2 sized tumors, and 25% of T3 sized tumors showed positivity (table No:6). The receptor status was found to be comparatively reduced in larger sized tumors as depicted. HER-2/neu over expression was noted in 2% of T1 sized tumors, 34% of T2 sized tumors and 0% of T3 sized tumors (table No: 7). This may be due to increased triple negative expression of tumors in present study population.

Correlation with nodal status: H.J. Huang et al [12] in their study of 1362 women with primary breast tumor found that Estrogen receptor positivity was less in nodal positive tumors. Puvitha et al [7] noticed that out of 33 patients 15 cases showed metastasis while 18 cases did not. Receptor positivity was found to be higher among the nodal metastasis negative patients 55.55% (10/18). HER-2/neu over expression was seen in 66.66% of nodal positive cases than the nodal negative patients which was 11.1 %.

In the present study out of 41 patients with nodal metastasis 12 patients showed receptor positivity, this accounts for 29% of cases. Whereas among 24 nodal metastasis negative patients 9 showed receptor positivity, this accounts for 38% (table No: 10). The pattern shows increased receptor positivity in node negative cases when compared to node positive cases. Out of 41 patients with nodal metastasis 17 showed her-2/neu over expression, this accounts for 41%. Out of 24 patients without nodal metastasis only 1 showed her-2/neu over expression, this accounts for only 4%. This shows that nodal metastasis is associated with over expression of her-2/neu which explains their aggressive nature.

Correlation of Estrogen, Progesterone receptor with HER-2/neu: H.J. Huang et al [12] in their study of 1362 women with primary breast tumor found an inverse relationship with receptor and oncoprotein expression.

This explains the cross-linkage between the two pathways of tumor growth. Francis G et al [13] in 2006 studied 591 tumors and concluded that more than 20% of HER-2/neu positive tumors showed moderate or strong staining for Estrogen receptors. Puvitha et al [9] in 2010 demonstrated that out of 33 cases two cases were Estrogen receptor- HER-2/neu positive. 4 cases were triple negative.

The findings demonstrated an inverse relation between receptor status and her2 expression. In the present study out of 100 cases 9 were hormone receptor positive and her-2/neu positive. 51 cases were triple negative (table No: 12). As demonstrated by the above studies the present

study also showed increased tendency of oncoprotein expression in hormone receptor negative cases.

Correlation of clinical stage and histopathological grade: Yang XR et al [14], El-sayed ME et al [15], syed BM et al [16], quayson SE et al [17] and ankita et al [18] in their respective studies demonstrated a positive correlation between clinical stage and histopathological grade. In concordance with the above studies the present study showed that higher clinical stage is associated with tumors of higher grade (table No: 13).

Correlation of Lymphnode Status with Histopathological Grade: Price GE et al [19], found that metastasis of carcinoma breast is mainly through lymphovascular invasion. Song JU et al [20], studied role of lymphovascular invasion as a positive prognostic marker for higher histopathological grade. In the present study it is observed that nodal metastasis is associated with more number of higher grade tumors. Out of 78 cases with nodal metastasis 53 were grade 2 and 13 were grade 3. Compared to 34 cases with no nodal metastasis in which 15 were grade 1 and 19 were grade 2 and there were no grade 3 tumors.

Summary

- The peak age of incidence of breast carcinoma in present study is 41 to 50 years.
- IAC grading of cytological smears is found to show high correlation with Histopathological picture. Hence this will assist to bring uniformity of reporting among pathologists and in predicting aggressiveness of tumor.
- Among the various histological variants of breast carcinoma, Invasive breast carcinoma – NOS type constituted 97%.
- Grade II tumors accounted for 68% of tumors in the present study population.
- Estrogen, Progesterone receptor or both are found to be positive in 34% while 66% showed negativity.
- HER-2 /neu over expression is seen in 24% of tumors and not seen in 76% of tumors.
- Out of 65 cases, 15 were T1, 46 were T2 and 4 cases were T3 tumors .smaller the tumor size more is the receptor positivity. This inverse relationship showed statistical significance (p value=0.005).
- HER-2/neu over expression showed a trend of increased positivity up to 5cm. tumors above 5cm did not show Her-2/nue over expression. This may be due to the increased number of triple negative cases in present study population.
- Change in histological grade did not show any major variation in receptor status in present study population. As grade 1, 2 and 3 tumors

showed receptor positivity of 28%, 34% and 33% respectively.

- Change in histological grade from grade 2 to grade 3 did not show any major variation in Her-2/neu expression.
- Out of 24 nodal negative patients 38% showed receptor positivity. And among 41 nodal positive patients 29% showed receptor positivity. Even though there is an inverse relation between nodal metastasis and receptor status, this did not show statistical significance.
- HER-2/neu over expression is observed in 41% of nodal positive patients, compared to 4% of nodal positive patients. This is statistically significant (P=0.001).
- Higher the Estrogen, Progesterone receptor positivity, lower was the HER-2/neu over expression. Even though an inverse relation between the receptor and HER-2/neu was observed, there is no statistical significance. Out of 100 cases 51 were triple negative. This might explain the incidence of higher percentage of triple negative tumors in Indian population.
- Advanced clinical stage showed strong correlation with higher histological grade. This is found to be statistically significant (p value=0.002)
- Lymphnode metastasis is found to be associated with higher histological grade of tumors. This is found to be statistically significant (p value=0.001)

Conclusion

IAC grading of cytology smears is found to be useful in standardization of reporting. Estrogen, progesterone positivity is more in smaller sized tumors. Her-2/nue over expression is seen among nodal positive cases.

Higher tumor grade is associated with advanced clinical stage. Lymphnode metastasis is associated with higher tumor grade. Incidence of triple negative tumors is more among Indian population when compared to western world.

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